

Titrimetric Determination of Ti(III) with Vanadium(V) and Vanadium(IV) using Cacotheline and Some Thiazine Dyes as Indicators[†]

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Titanium(III) can be determined with sodium vanadate or vanadyl sulphate using cacotheline and some thiazine dyes (methylene blue, azure A, azure B, azure C, thionine, new methylene blue and toluidine blue) as indicators in 10-12*M* phosphoric acid medium. This procedure can also be used for the estimation of Vanadium(IV) and Vanadium(V) with standard titanium(III) chloride solution.

TITANIUM(III) was determined with vanadate by direct and indirect¹ titrimetric methods. Similarly titanium(III) was determined with vanadium(IV) by earlier workers^{2,3}. So far neutral red, phenosafranine and safranine-T are used as indicators in presence of oxalic acid for the determination of titanium(III) with vanadate⁴. The literature survey reveals that no visual method of estimation of titanium(III) with vanadium(IV) was reported using an indicator. In this paper we present the details of the use of cacotheline and some thiazine dyes (methylene blue, azure A, azure B, azure C, thionine, new methylene blue, and toluidine blue) as indicators for the determination of titanium(III) with sodium vanadate and vanadyl sulphate.

Experimental

Reagents :

Sodium Vanadate Solution : 0.05*N* sodium vanadate solution is prepared and standardised.

Vanadium(IV) Solution : Vanadium(IV) sulphate was prepared by sulphite reduction method and standardised according to the procedure given by Dikshitulu and Gopala Rao⁵.

Ti(III) Chloride Solution : 0.1*N* titanium(III) chloride solution was prepared in 2*N* hydrochloric acid and standardised according to the procedure of Breit⁶.

0.2% cacotheline and 0.1% aqueous solutions of thiazine dyes are prepared.

Procedure : 40 ml. of syrupy phosphoric acid is taken in the titration vessel. Carbon dioxide is passed through it for 10 minutes. Then an aliquot volume of titanium(III) chloride is run down into the titration vessel. Then the contents are titrated with V(V) or V(IV) solution to the appearance of yellow colour in case of cacotheline (0.5 ml. of

solution added near the end-point) or greenish blue colour in the case of thiazine dyes (0.1 ml. of dye solution added from the beginning). Some typical results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE—1 : DETERMINATION OF TITANIUM(III) WITH VANADIUM (V) AND VANADIUM(IV) IN 11*M* PHOSPHORIC ACID MEDIUM

Indicator used	Amount of Ti(III) (m. moles × 10 ⁻¹)	
	Taken (through dichromate method)	Found (through authors' method)
	With Vanadate	
Cacotheline	6.285	6.281
	1.839	1.840
Methylene blue	6.075	6.091
	1.823	1.832
New methylene blue	6.015	6.022
	2.406	2.405
Thionine	5.832	5.839
	2.187	2.198
Toluidine blue	2.406	2.410
	6.015	6.022
Azure A	6.050	6.068
	2.290	2.298
Azure B	5.808	5.816
	3.630	3.641
Azure C	6.015	6.022
	1.203	1.205
	With Vanadium(IV)	
Cacotheline	6.532	6.537
	1.645	1.646
Methylene blue	6.090	6.040
	3.420	3.430
New methylene blue	1.094	1.099
	6.017	6.030
Thionine	6.270	6.271
	3.215	3.216
Azure A	6.156	6.164
	2.730	2.734
Azure B	6.199	6.217
	2.029	2.035
Azure C	6.199	6.217
	1.690	1.698
Toluidine blue	2.188	2.185
	6.017	6.030

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By taking vanadium(V) or vanadium(IV) solutions in the titration vessel and titrating with titanium(III) chloride according to the above procedure, it has been observed that vanadium(V) (0.24 m. moles to 0.60 m. moles) and vanadium(IV) (0.15 m. moles to 0.62 m. moles) can be determined with an average error of 0.3% and 0.35% respectively.

Discussion

An attempt to determine titanium(III) with vanadium(V) or vanadium(IV) in hydrochloric or sulphuric acid medium has been met with failure. In the case of vanadium(V) as an oxidimetric reagent in lower acid concentrations (HCl or H₂SO₄) end-point is not obtained. This is due to the interference of vanadium(III) produced with the indicator reaction. But at higher acidities the interference of vanadium(III) in the indicator reaction is eliminated. Still higher values are obtained for titanium(III). This is due to the low oxidising action of vanadium(IV) (intermediate) on the reduced form of the indicator. Similarly in the case of vanadium(IV) as an oxidant, the end-point cannot be detected either in low or high acid (HCl or H₂SO₄) concentrations.

Gopala Rao and Dikshitulu⁷ reported that the formal potential of V(IV)/V(III) couple increases from 0.379-0.702 as phosphoric acid concentration increases from 0.5-12 M. From this observation, the authors have found the determination of Ti(III) with feasible vanadium(V) and vanadium(IV) in strong

phosphoric acid medium, where the two difficulties experienced in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media can be easily overcome.

Interferences :

Na⁺, K⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄⁻, acetate, oxalate, borate and tartarate do not interfere.

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References

1. A. RIUS and C. A. DIAZ-FLORES, *An. Real. Soc. Espan. Fisic. Quim.*, 150, 46B, 289.
2. C. DEL FRESNO and E. MAILOT *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 214, 73.
3. B. V. S. R. MURTHY and G. G. RAO, *Talanta*, 1961, 8, 547.
4. B. V. S. R. MURTHY and G. G. RAO, *Talanta*, 1961, 8, 438.
5. L. S. A. DIKSHITULU and G. GOPALA RAO, *Talanta*, 1962, 9, 857.
6. J. E. BREIT, *J. Assoc. Agr. Chem.*, 1947, 30, 504 ; 1948, 31, 573 ; 1949, 32, 589.
7. G. GOPALA RAO and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, *Talanta*, 1963, 10, 295.